

SOLO PARENT EMPLOYEES' AWARENESS OF REPUBLIC ACT 8972 AND WORK PERFORMANCE IN XYZ CORPORATION

Geoffrey Julius D. Tutor

*School of Graduate Studies , Laguna College of Business & Arts, Calamba City,
Laguna, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the awareness of solo parent employees within XYZ Corporation regarding the Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000 (RA 8972) and its impact on their work performance. The research focused on three variables: Legal Literacy, Privileges and Benefits, and Factors affecting the Act's implementation. The study applied Legal Consciousness Theory and Social Exchange Theory to understand how awareness of legal rights influenced behavior and decision-making in the workplace. It also explored the employees' performance across Task Performance, Contextual Performance, and Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB). Using a researcher-made survey and a sample of 59 employees, the study found a modest positive correlation between awareness of RA 8972 and work performance (r values between .164 and .315). Statistical analysis confirmed a significant relationship (p-values of .015, .041, and .045), suggesting that greater awareness could improve performance. The study recommended an action plan to enhance the Solo Parent Awareness Program at XYZ Corporation, aiming to create a more supportive and inclusive environment for solo parent employees, ultimately boosting their work performance and well-being.

Keywords: *Solo Parent Welfare Act of 2000, Legal Consciousness, Social Exchange Theory, Psychological Empowerment Theory, Three Big Domains of Work Performance*

INTRODUCTION

A solo parent, as defined by the Solo Parents Welfare Act of 2000, is the only one taking care of their child or children. It could be a mom or a dad who has full responsibility for their kids, someone who takes care of their child or children by themselves without a partner. This also includes women who are expecting a baby but are not married and those who have legally adopted a child.

Currently, single parenting is increasingly becoming a prominent trend, acknowledged by every nation as both an economic and social challenge, especially in developing nations such as the Philippines. Single parents are a prevalent presence in society, not solely within urban areas, stemming from various circumstances like divorce, legal separation, the use of assisted reproductive technologies such as In Vitro Fertilization, and the engagement of surrogate mothers, often chosen as a personal preference by individuals.

Solo parenthood is now transcending geographical boundaries, echoing as a universal experience amidst the diverse tapestry of human existence. Across continents and cultures, individuals find themselves navigating the intricate journey of single-handedly raising and providing for their children. Recognizing the multifaceted challenges inherent in solo parenthood, governments worldwide have instituted legislative measures to support and empower solo parents.

Here to feature, France-Press (2022) published an article in *Inquirer* entitled "Unwed and unwanted: Chinese single mothers fight for rights" which stated that there should be greater recognition and respect for single mothers as more individuals opted not to marry. According to a report released in 2019 by a research institute associated with the Chinese government, it was estimated that China's population included over 19 million single mothers, encompassing women who had gone through divorce or were widowed. This statistic shed light on the significant number of women in China who were raising children on their own due to various life circumstances, underscoring the diverse composition of family structures within the country.

Moreover, Jordan et al (2019) released a report in the Publication Office of the European Union entitled "Mechanisms supporting single parents across the European Union," which highlighted the numerous challenges faced by single-parent households, including employment and financial stability. Single parents often found themselves solely responsible for both providing for their families financially and caring for their children without the assistance of a partner. This situation can lead to significant stress and hardships in their lives. Single parents encountered a variety of obstacles that exacerbate their circumstances.

Additionally, several countries such as Austria, France, and Ireland, offered supplementary financial aid specifically for single-parent households, in addition to other forms of assistance. In the United Kingdom, families headed by a single parent may receive additional financial support if their income was low. It was important to note that

these benefits were not limited solely to single-parent families; rather, they reflected a broader societal responsibility toward children's welfare. When an individual became a parent, regardless of their marital status, they bore the financial obligation to contribute towards the upbringing and care of their child. Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2022)

According to the Philippine Information Technology (2024), the Department of Health and the University of the Philippines-National Institutes of Health released a report revealing that there were approximately 15 million solo parents in the Philippines. Remarkably, 95% of these solo parents were women, while the remaining 5% were men. This data highlighted a significant demographic trend, indicating a substantial presence of solo-parent households in the country.

To provide support to solo parents in the Philippines, President Estrada introduced several initiatives and regulations aimed at assisting single-parent households. The efforts began in 2000 when President Joseph E. Estrada signed into law Republic Act 8972, which significantly improved the circumstances of single parents and expanded the rights of families headed by single parents. This legislation delineated specific rights and benefits, including provisions for leave credits, flexible work arrangements, and educational assistance for single parents. Isla (2023) issued directives emphasizing the critical importance of solo parents being fully informed about their rights and responsibilities. This awareness extends beyond personal benefits to encompass the holistic well-being of their children. Additionally, she underscored the need for solo parents to have a clear understanding of the support services provided by local governments. This comprehensive understanding enables solo parents to effectively access and utilize available resources aimed at supporting their family dynamics and ensuring their children's welfare.

For over a decade, the Solo Parents Welfare Act of 2000 has been in force, yet concerns persist regarding its implementation. Many questions emerge, including: Do employed solo parents fully understand the Act's requirements? Are private companies, such as XYZ Corporation, familiar with its provisions? Will compliance with this law positively or negatively impact employee productivity? The primary aim of this study was to explore solo parents' awareness of RA 8972 and its correlation with their work performance. Ultimately, the study sought to develop an action plan focusing on enhancing solo parents' awareness of RA 8972 provisions, assessing the extent of its implementation, and identifying factors influencing the execution of the Solo Parents Welfare Act of 2000, to ensure compliance and examine its potential impact on employee work performance.

Research Questions

This study sought to find the correlation between the awareness of solo parent employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and work performance of solo parent employees working in XYZ Corporation. Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of awareness of solo parent employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) in XYZ Corporation as assessed by employees in terms of:
 - 1.1 Legal Literacy (Legal Definition of Solo Parent)
 - 1.2 Privileges and Benefits, and
 - 1.3 Factors that Affect the Implementation of this Act?
2. What is the level of work performance of solo parent in XYZ Corporation as assessed by the solo parent employees in terms of:
 - 2.1 Task Performance
 - 2.2 Contextual Performance (Organizational Citizenship Behavior), and
 - 2.3 Counterproductive Work Behavior?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of awareness of solo parent employees to RA 8972 (SOLO PARENTS' WELFARE ACT OF 2000) and the work performance of employees working in XYZ Corporation?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

RA 8972 Solo Parents Welfare Act of 2000

Many people were raising children on their own as single parents. They were people who belonged to the church, coworkers/employees, business owners, daughters, mothers, fathers, and grandparents. In an article published by Zuckerman (2020).entitled "Single Parents", it was mentioned that 86 out of 100 single-parent households in the United States were taken care of by moms. Fifty-seven percent (57%) of young women who belonged to the Millennial generation were raising their children without a partner. And as of the end of 2021, one out of every four American homes was taken care of by one parent.

Moreover, a report from Kluchand Crabtree (2020) entitled "Single Moms Struggling Worldwide, Particularly in U.S." stated that in 2019, almost half of single moms (exactly 44%) in the world had a hard time getting enough food. Furthermore, around 40% of single mothers in the United States struggled with food, while 27% struggled with housing. Lithuania had 36%, Estonia had 36%, France had 30%, the US had 27%, and Republic of North Macedonia (24%) had the greatest number of single mothers unable to afford housing in 2019. Furthermore, in 2019 alone, 65% of women in Sub-Saharan Africa struggled to feed their families. Additionally, 15% of unmarried mothers in the United States lacked health insurance coverage, and single-parent households in London were projected to face a financial shortfall of £2,400 per year by 2021.

Additionally, according to Alngag (2022), being a solo parent involved a range of responsibilities too, including tending to their children's health, emotional well-being, and overall welfare. In cases where a parent was unable to fulfill all of these duties, it could adversely affect their child's mental health and their ability to provide care. Children in single-parent households often shouldered a significant portion of household chores, encouraging them to share responsibilities and become more self-sufficient compared to

their peers. Additionally, solo parents were more inclined to involve their children in decision-making processes compared to parents who had a partner.

Furthermore, Maldonado and Nieuwenhuis (2019) also highlighted in their article entitled "The triple bind of single-parent families" that there were significant challenges faced by single parents, emphasizing the hardships they endured in various aspects of life. They noted that single parents often encountered difficulties in the workplace, including lower wages and unfair treatment. Additionally, insufficient financial resources and lack of support posed obstacles to effectively caring for their families, exacerbated by limited access to quality employment opportunities. Policies designed to assist single parents frequently fell short, failing to adequately address their needs in areas such as socialization, emotional management, and financial stability compared to families with two financially secure parents. The article underscored the imperative for government and private sector intervention to support single parents, suggesting measures such as implementing employment policies that included paid leave, ensuring fairness in the workplace, and ensuring sufficient income to enable comfortable living standards.

In line with this, Schulte and Pabst (2021) highlighted significant disparities in family leave policies across different countries. In the United States, workers were entitled to up to 12 weeks of unpaid leave to care for a family member, a provision applicable universally rather than exclusively to parents. In contrast, countries like Norway provided better support, offering married or cohabiting parents 10 to 15 paid days annually to care for sick children under 12, while single parents received between 20 and 30 paid days off each year. Finland went further, allowing each parent 164 days off every seven months, or 328 days for a single parent, with these periods fully paid by the government. Consequently, some nations including Belgium and South Korea, recognized the added challenges faced by single parents and consequently offered them more financial support compared to married or partnered parents. This acknowledgement stemmed from the understanding that single parents often bear sole responsibility for childcare. By advocating for policy reforms that would ensure equitable support for all parents worldwide, the lives of single-parent families can be improved.

Correspondingly, there was limited research addressing the challenges faced by single parents. According to Stack and Meredith's (2019) publication entitled "The Impact of Financial Hardship on Single Parents: An Exploration of the Journey from Social Distress to Seeking Help," financial struggles among solo parents adversely affected their emotional well-being. Parents reported difficulties affording essentials like food and fuel, often making sacrifices to ensure their children's needs were met. Such circumstances compelled individuals to make difficult choices, such as accepting low-paying jobs with flexible schedules or prioritizing between purchasing groceries or paying bills. Additional dilemmas involved relying on others for support rather than paying for costly childcare or opting to stay home to care for their children instead of outsourcing childcare responsibilities.

Consequently, single parents in the United States encountered obstacles in achieving career advancement due to financial constraints, leading to reliance on low-

wage employment or choosing to prioritize childcare responsibilities. This predicament often led to feelings of isolation, anxiety, despair, paranoia, and even thoughts of suicide, highlighting the mental health challenges faced by single parents. It was imperative to acknowledge these consequences and examine the underlying economic factors contributing to distress, as emphasized by Gilmore (2021).

On a serious note, it was crucial for companies to actively recruit and promote single parents, implement work programs and schedules that recognized that all employees had their personal obligations lived outside of work, and fostered an inclusive workplace culture. Additionally, managers should have engaged single parents in discussions about their career aspirations and regularly checked in with them, creating an environment where seeking assistance was encouraged. To prevent burnout, organizations should adopt creative and flexible approaches to structuring and managing labor. Dr. Stephanie Lee (2021), senior director of the Child Mind Institute, believed that firms should have avoided normalizing overworking and allowed employees greater flexibility and autonomy over the time, manner, and location of their work.

Likewise, Yost (2021), founder of the Flex+Strategy Group, stated that firms should have exchanged best practices and focused on worker engagement, challenge, and meaningful work. Moss (2021), the author of *The Burnout Epidemic*, advised that firms should focus on "work hygiene" to ensure that salary, benefits, corporate regulations, and working conditions were fair and healthful. Organizations could have strengthened paid time off policy, supported public efforts for universal paid family and medical leave, paid sick leave, and paid vacation leave, and assisted with childcare. Organizations had to make an effort to understand their workforce's care requirements and to commit to doing more. They could have also advocated for policies that supported working parents and modified regulations to account for the particular limits that single parents faced.

Presently, based on the report by Reyes (2021) entitled "Solo Parents' Poverty Situation in the Philippines: A Qualitative and Policy Evaluation Study", with 2.9 million single parents classified as widowed or separated, solo parenting had become more common in the Philippines. RA 8972 responded to the requirements of single parents by offering comprehensive programs and services. It emphasized the family as the nation's cornerstone by guaranteeing its complete development. The Solo Parents Welfare Act of 2000 and the Philippine Constitution of 1986 both gave financial aid to bereaved and abandoned parents, as well as unmarried moms. Article 212 of the Family Code mandated the current parent to continue exercising parental control over the children in the absence or death of either parent.

Commonly, it was difficult for anybody to balance job and family, but it was especially difficult for single parents who didn't have a partner to support them. Sometimes parents had to miss work to care for a sick child or attend a school function. But what if they couldn't find somebody to look after their child? Actually, "solo-parent friendly" workplaces were required. According to the Solo Parents Welfare Act and the Family Code, offices had to include childcare centers and areas for mothers to breastfeed. Single parents could then take seven additional paid days off for childcare, in addition to

what they were already entitled to under the law. However, according to Castaneda (2021), some firms might not have followed the guidelines and might not have recruited single parents at all. They did not wish to spend additional funds on employees and their perks. This was unjust to employees, but they might have argued that they had to do so to continue in business, especially when the Pandemic had reduced their revenues.

In relation to the Legal Consciousness Theory (Horák et al., 2021) stated that individuals develop their legal consciousness through interactions with legal institutions, social networks, and cultural norms, shaping their understanding of their rights and obligations within the legal system. In this case, the widespread dissemination of information about the Solo Parent Act through government agencies, media channels, community organizations, and advocacy groups played a crucial role in raising awareness among solo parent employees. These efforts served to educate individuals about their legal rights and benefits under the law, thereby contributing to their legal consciousness regarding the Solo Parent Act.

Furthermore, Legerde (2023) stated that the Solo Parent Act addressed a significant social issue in the Philippines, which likely generated substantial attention and discussion among the general populace. This societal discourse helped to reinforce awareness and understanding of the Act among solo parent employees, aligning with Legal Consciousness Theory's emphasis on the influence of societal norms and values on legal awareness. Moreover, the provisions of the Solo Parent Act directly impacted a substantial portion of the population in the Philippines, including solo parents themselves and their families. As a result, many individuals had personal or familial connections to solo parenthood, leading to increased awareness and interest in the Act. This aligned with Legal Consciousness Theory's premise that legal awareness was shaped by personal experiences and social relationships.

Additionally, initiatives such as Solo Parent's Week, which aimed to raise awareness about the rights and challenges faced by solo parents, contributed to the dissemination of information about the Solo Parent Act. By organizing activities, seminars, and programs, these initiatives helped to reinforce legal consciousness among solo parent employees and promoted understanding and empathy towards their situations. Furthermore, some private sector employers actively collaborated with DSWD in informing their employees about the provisions of RA 8972 and the benefits available to solo parents. This was through employee orientation programs, company newsletters, or dedicated information sessions. On February 23, 2023, at the Liberman Sports Complex in Pandan, Antique, the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) Field Office–Antique, in collaboration with the Pandan Municipal Social Welfare and Development Office (MSWDO) under the direction of Ms. Mary Ann A. Samulde, hosted an orientation on RA 8972. For them to utilize their rights and benefits, 407 single parents received orientation, and the legal definition of "solo parent" was discussed as well (pandan-antique.gov.ph).

Furthermore, Ramirez's (2019) article on Legal Awareness and Social Change: "The Case of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act in the Philippines" provided valuable insights

into the role of legal consciousness theory in shaping individuals' understanding and awareness of legal norms, rights, and obligations. In the context of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act (RA 8972) in the Philippines, legal consciousness theory suggested that individuals who possessed a higher level of legal literacy regarding the definition of solo parent status were more likely to recognize and assert their rights under the law.

In addition, Ramirez's (2019) study explored how awareness and understanding of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act among solo parents were influenced by their legal literacy. It investigated how familiarity with the legal definition of solo parent status correlated with individual's ability to access benefits and protections provided by the law. By analyzing the relationship between legal literacy and behavior or decision-making among solo parents, the study had shed light on the empowering role of legal consciousness in navigating the legal system effectively. Ramirez's (2019) research highlighted the importance of initiatives aimed at enhancing legal literacy among solo parents, such as educational campaigns, legal clinics, or community outreach programs. By increasing awareness and understanding of their rights and obligations under the Solo Parents' Welfare Act, solo parents could have better advocacy for themselves and access the support and resources available to them.

Additionally, conservative community attitudes towards single parenthood fostered stigma and discrimination against solo parents, which often deterred them from seeking information or support regarding RA 8972. The fear of social judgment or exclusion may have inhibited solo parents from participating in awareness campaigns or seeking help from local authorities or support networks. The lack of community support and acceptance likely contributed to feelings of marginalization and isolation among solo parents, influencing their awareness levels and overall well-being (singleparentrights, 2024).

Similarly, Tan's (2022) study on The Impact of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act on Legal Consciousness and Social Perceptions in the Philippines, published in the Asian Journal of Legal Studies, provided additional insights into the application of legal consciousness theory in the context of solo parent awareness and empowerment. Legal consciousness theory emphasized how individuals' understanding and awareness of legal norms, rights, and obligations influenced their behavior and decision-making. In the context of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act (RA 8972) in the Philippines, Tan's study explored how the implementation and impact of the law contributed to the development of legal consciousness among solo parents. The research investigated how awareness and understanding of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act influenced solo parents' perceptions of their legal rights and entitlements, as well as their ability to navigate the legal system effectively.

Moreover, Tan's (2022) study also examined the role of legal literacy in shaping solo parents' experiences with the Solo Parents' Welfare Act. It explored how individuals who possessed a higher level of legal literacy regarding the definition of solo parent status were more likely to recognize and assert their rights under the law. By analyzing the relationship between legal literacy and access to benefits and protections provided by the Solo Parents' Welfare Act, the study highlighted the empowering effects of legal

consciousness on solo parent advocacy and empowerment. Furthermore, Tan's research assessed the broader social perceptions and attitudes toward solo parenthood and the Solo Parents' Welfare Act in the Philippines. By examining how the law had influenced societal norms and values regarding solo parenting, the study provided insights into the impact of legal reforms on social perceptions and attitudes towards marginalized groups such as solo parents.

In addition, Yap et al. (2023) discussed the process for solo parents to obtain benefits and privileges under the Solo Parents Welfare Act of 2000. According to them, solo parents are required to apply for a solo parent ID from the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD). The application process involves visiting the DSWD office and submitting the necessary documentation. A social worker verifies the completeness of the paperwork before recording the application in the Registry of Solo Parents, assigning an appropriate case number. After submission, the ID is typically issued within 30 days and is valid for one year, with the option to renew.

Notably, many Filipino single parents were unaware of the substantial advantages associated with obtaining a Solo Parent ID. This identification enabled them to access various benefits, starting with Parental Leaves. Governed by Civil Service Commission Memorandum Circular No. 08, series 2004, solo parent employees with at least one year of tenure could take up to 7 days of parental leave annually, in addition to their regular leave entitlements. To qualify, they needed to notify their employer in advance and present their Solo Parent ID. These leaves could be used for pivotal moments in their child's life, educational commitments, healthcare needs, and other caregiving responsibilities. Furthermore, Flexible Work Schedules were also available, allowing single parents to adjust their work hours, provided it did not disrupt operations. Employers were prohibited from discriminating against single parents in terms of benefits or working conditions.

In addition to these provisions, the Solo Parents Welfare Act offered a comprehensive array of government benefits, including Educational, Housing, Medical Assistance, and a Comprehensive Package of Social Development and Welfare Services. It's crucial to note that these benefits were contingent upon maintaining solo parent status, ceasing upon conditions such as marriage or the adoption of children by others.

Santos's (2021) study titled "Public Discourse and Policy Implementation: Analyzing Media Representations of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act in the Philippines," published in the *Journal of Philippine Studies*, delved into how societal discourse influenced perceptions of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act (RA 8972). This legislation provides various privileges and benefits aimed at supporting solo parents and their children, rooted in the principles of the Social Exchange Theory. According to this theory, individuals engage in relationships expecting reciprocal benefits. In the context of RA 8972, these benefits include flexible work arrangements, anti-discrimination measures, parental leave entitlements, and access to social services. Santos's research analyzed media representations of the law, exploring how they shaped public understanding and attitudes towards solo parenthood and the support mechanisms available.

Moreover, Santos (2021) also examined the role of media advocacy and public discourse in promoting the implementation of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act. By spotlighting the experiences of solo parents through media narratives, the study aimed to increase awareness and comprehension of the benefits provided under RA 8972. This approach sought to foster a sense of mutual benefit and reciprocity among societal members, aligning with the tenets of the Social Exchange Theory. Despite requirements for solo parents to participate in orientations or seminars conducted by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) or accredited local entities, many employed solo parents remained unaware of their entitlements. This gap in awareness could be attributed to various factors, including limited access to information and language barriers, highlighting ongoing challenges in ensuring widespread knowledge and utilization of the law's provisions.

Moreover, the analysis of three research projects conducted in Zamboanga City provided valuable insights into various localized topics. These studies focused on a range of aspects related to single-parent households, including the challenges they faced, strategies for coping, their financial well-being, social support systems, and the impacts of the Expanded Solo Parents Welfare Act (RA 11861). To assess the effect of RA 11861 on the financial security of single-parent households in Zamboanga City, Tan and Lim (2020) undertook quantitative research. Their findings indicated that the implementation of livelihood programs had led to an increase in the income of single parents, resulting in improved financial stability and a decrease in the percentage of single-parent households living in poverty.

Also, Gonzales et al.'s (2021) study examined the impact of educational support provided by RA 11861 on the academic achievement of children in single-parent families in Zamboanga City. The research revealed that the provision of support services and educational grants resulted in increased school attendance and improved academic performance among children raised by single parents.

In addition, Dela Cruz and Reyes (2022) conducted a comprehensive analysis of the overall effectiveness of RA 11861 in Zamboanga City. Their study evaluated the accessibility, utilization, and satisfaction levels of single parents regarding the legal benefits and services offered by the law. The findings highlighted areas for improvement, such as enhancing awareness and streamlining application procedures, to ensure that targeted assistance reaches all eligible single-parent households efficiently.

Additionally, RA 11861, also known as the "Expanded Solo Parents Welfare Act," was enacted to provide additional assistance and privileges to solo parents, thereby aligning with the government's commitment to promoting social justice. This legislation builds upon RA 8972, the "Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000," to further support solo parents in their roles and address their specific needs (DSWD 2022).

Also, Keum's (2023) research on "The Impact of Language Barriers on Family Law", published in *Modern Family Law*, shed light on the challenges posed by language barriers in accessing legal information and understanding family law. Keum's findings

highlighted how language barriers could hinder effective communication and comprehension of legal documents or government announcements related to family law, such as RA 8972. The research underscored the importance of addressing language barriers to ensure that solo parent employees could fully understand their rights and entitlements under RA 8972. It was also stated that despite the requirement for solo parents to participate in orientations or seminars organized by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) or accredited local entities, many employed solo parents still remained not aware of their entitlements. This lack of awareness may stem from various factors, including limited access to information and language barriers, highlighting persistent challenges in ensuring broad awareness and effective utilization of the law's provisions.

Moreover, awareness of RA 8972 was significantly influenced also by several factors that affected the implementation of this Act as stated by Alngag (2022). Firstly, the absence of local support groups left solo parent employees with limited access to resources and guidance regarding their rights under the law. Additionally, the Act might not have been deemed a priority issue within the community, leading to a lack of formal seminars or educational sessions conducted by entities such as the Barangay Development Council. Furthermore, the absence of comprehensive support services provided by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) could have diminished the perceived value of RA 8972, leaving solo parent employees unaware of the benefits available to them, such as livelihood assistance and educational support. Lastly, conservative societal attitudes towards single parenthood and the lack of awareness among local authorities further hindered efforts to raise awareness about RA 8972 among solo parent employees, highlighting the need for targeted education and support initiatives within both the workplace and the broader community.

Additionally, studies examining community awareness of legal provisions and welfare acts frequently revealed gaps in comprehension among the general populace. For instance, a study conducted by Sharma and Singh (2020) entitled "Awareness and Perception of Legal Rights Among Rural Communities in India" highlighted the limited awareness of legal rights and protections within rural communities. Understanding these disparities was crucial for assessing the effectiveness of legal frameworks in empowering marginalized populations. For solo parents, such research could serve as a tool to gauge their understanding of legal rights, encompassing concepts like labor rights and entitlements to social welfare schemes. This assessment aided in elucidating why issues pertinent to solo parents, including legal rights under welfare acts, might not have held priority within the community.

Furthermore, reports from entities such as the United Nations Development Programme Annual Report.(2023) or the World Bank offered insights into the resource limitations confronting local authorities. These authorities grappled with significant financial constraints, as their budgets were often insufficient to address the multifaceted needs of their communities. Challenges stemmed from various factors, including restricted revenue sources, reliance on central government transfers, and competing expenditure priorities. Moreover, many local authorities contended with shortages in

human resources, particularly in rural and remote regions. Issues such as inadequate staff capacity, high turnover rates, and difficulties in recruiting qualified personnel hindered the effective implementation of local governance initiatives. Furthermore, deficiencies in infrastructure, such as insufficient roads, water supply systems, and public facilities, presented additional obstacles for local authorities in delivering essential services. The lack of access to basic infrastructure not only hampered economic development but also impacted the quality of life for residents, including solo parents.

Likewise, the absence of awareness among members of the Barangay Development Council could have led to missed opportunities for collaborating with government agencies, NGOs, and other stakeholders to promote awareness and implement supportive programs for solo parents. Without active engagement from local authorities and community leaders, solo parents may have faced restricted access to reliable information and support services, thereby affecting their awareness and ability to navigate their rights under RA 8972 (Philippine Commission on Women, 2023).

As a final point, community surveys or consultations orchestrated by local governments or non-profit organizations revealed that priorities and responsibilities extended far beyond addressing solo parent rights. These encompassed a spectrum of vital domains including infrastructure development, public health and safety, education, economic development, environmental protection, and emergency and disaster management. Reports from esteemed organizations like the Pew Research Center (2022) indicated that strengthening the economy held the highest priority rating at 71%, while addressing drug addiction ranked considerably lower at 31%.

Work Performance

Work performance was critical for human resource management; it was referred to as the "ultimate dependent variable" in the field. Its evaluation and analysis were essential for many organizational activities such as staff selection, salary and incentives, and training. In relation to Solo parents, these three dimensions were considered greatly as they contributed to the organizational goals. The three major domains of job performance were task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior. Each of these parameters was defined in the manner of Rotundo and Sackett (2022)

Additionally, Gunyakti et al. (2024) stated the effectiveness with which an employee executed activities that contributed to the organization's technical core, either directly by performing a component of its technological process or indirectly by providing it with essential resources or services, was characterized as task performance. For a solo parent, performing office jobs eight hours a day, with a high level of daily work pressure, and handling independently the stress within their home, could arguably perform well particularly if they had the proper support and the knowledge of their rights and privileges under RA 8972. Employed solo parents were secured under the operation of law for professional working privileges; however, companies needed someone who could

perform and could work under pressure with results, making it a 50/50 decision for the majority of companies to hire a solo parent employee.

Moreover, Hetland (2022) introduced two types of job demands called hindrance and challenge job demands in his research article entitled “Daily work pressure and Task performance: The moderating role of recovery and sleep”. He explained that difficult tasks at work that did not help one learn or improve much were called hindrance job demands. Common things that could make work difficult were conflicting job responsibilities, too many rules and paperwork to deal with, and worry about job stability. These problems could get in the way of emotional and mental needs. On the other hand, challenging job demands, like having a lot of work to do, difficult tasks, and deadlines to meet, could be tough to handle. But if one worked hard to manage them well, it could help them learn, grow, and achieve their goals. Sometimes, when one had to finish work quickly, they had to use a lot of energy. But if they finished the work before the time was up, they could feel proud of themselves and get better at doing it. Relating this to solo parents, they wanted to know if the awareness of RA 8972 specific on the professional working privileges could affect the challenge-hindrance stressor model under performance tasks. This might have had an impact, but it wasn't known yet up to what extent.

In addition, the study by Meier et al. (2019) showed that parents felt like they could never do enough when it came to working and taking care of their kids. Even if they spent a lot of time with them, they still felt guilty about not spending enough. According to recent surveys by Pew Research Center, 56% of moms who worked said it was hard to manage both their job and their family. Furthermore, 37 out of every 100 moms said they always felt like they did not have enough time. This happened more often to moms who had jobs outside the home, compared to moms who didn't work outside the home. Working moms were more likely to believe that they were doing an excellent or very good job at raising their children compared to those who didn't work. About two-thirds of the people surveyed were happy, but only one-third of them said they were very happy.

Drawing upon the insights from Brewer and Chen's (2020) study, it was evident that individuals' personal values wielded considerable influence over their attitudes, actions, and overall outcomes within the workplace. When there was a harmonious alignment between personal values and task objectives, it set the stage for a conducive work environment characterized by heightened levels of performance, dedication, and job satisfaction among employees. Moreover, for solo parents, a profound belief that their work resonated with their intrinsic values could fuel increased enthusiasm, commitment, and efficacy in task execution. Personal values often served as potent wellsprings of intrinsic motivation, propelling individuals towards excellence in their professional endeavors and facilitating meaningful contributions to organizational objectives. Consequently, when individuals perceived a strong resonance between their values and the tasks they undertook, they were more inclined to exhibit heightened engagement, vitality, and steadfast commitment to delivering exemplary outcomes.

Furthermore, Brewer and Chen's (2020) study also highlighted that individuals who perceived their work as congruent with their personal values tended to experience a

heightened sense of purpose and contentment in their professional roles. This intrinsic sense of purpose served as a valuable reward, motivating individuals to dedicate effort and focus to their responsibilities, thereby resulting in improved performance and satisfaction levels. Within the context of solo parents, employees who prioritized values such as integrity, fairness, and social responsibility were inclined to exhibit ethical conduct and engage in behaviors that promoted the common good, ultimately benefiting task execution and organizational achievements.

Similarly, the study by Li et al. (2020) focused on the relationship between empowering leadership, work-family enrichment, and mediating factors such as task meaningfulness and family-supportive supervisor behaviors, and hypothetical insights could still be drawn. The study found that an empowering leadership style encouraged employees to take ownership of their tasks and provided them with autonomy in decision-making. When employees felt empowered to make meaningful contributions and exercised discretion in how they approached their work, they were more likely to demonstrate high levels of task performance. It was also revealed that empowering leadership was associated with promoting a supportive work environment that valued work-life balance. Leaders who demonstrated understanding and flexibility regarding employees' family commitments and personal needs created a positive organizational culture that fostered employee well-being. Similarly, with the situation of the majority of solo parents, when they felt supported in managing their work and family responsibilities, they were better able to focus on their tasks and perform at a high level.

The second dimension was contextual performance, also referred to as organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Contextual performance extended beyond traditional work responsibilities. According to Bhardwaj and Kalia (2021), Contextual performance, also known as "discretionary extra-role behavior", was evident in activities such as counseling coworkers, establishing social networks inside a company, and going above and beyond for the organization. A large part of an organization's responsibility was to ensure that its personnel accomplished their jobs properly. Performing well in their whole work environment had recently become equally as crucial as performing well in their specialized job obligations. Experts increasingly believed that completing a task successfully was not the sole method to assess work effectiveness.

Moreover, Nini (2019) stated that one of the primary reasons contextual performance was included in the measurement of work performance was that it affected the quality of human resource activities. Work performance was inextricably tied to the organization's goals and mission. As a result, judgments on how to assess work performance and the relative weight given to task versus contextual behaviors had significant implications for human resource strategies.

Furthermore, while task performance was important, contextual performance improved the organizational environment by developing social networks. Nini (2019) stated that employees who participated in contextual performance contributed to the organization's culture and atmosphere. Because people volunteered for extra work,

persevered with passion, and supported and collaborated with others, contextual performance had the potential to revolutionize the business.

A different view, based on the study by Lam and Liang (2019), suggested that despite the presence of empowering leadership, there was a misalignment between employees' personal goals and the broader organizational objectives. While empowering leadership encouraged voice behavior by creating opportunities for employees to contribute ideas and suggestions, employees might not have perceived these behaviors as contributing to their personal goals or career advancement within the organization. As a result, they might have chosen not to engage in discretionary behaviors associated with contextual performance, such as offering suggestions for improvement or taking on additional tasks beyond their formal job roles.

Elaborating further, Lam and Liang (2019) identified that while empowering leadership encouraged voice behavior and offered opportunities for employees to contribute ideas and suggestions, solo parents might have perceived these behaviors as conflicting with their primary goal of balancing work and family responsibilities. In many cases, solo parents prioritized their family's well-being and the need to fulfill caregiving responsibilities over career advancement within the organization. As a result, they might have been less inclined to engage in discretionary behaviors associated with contextual performance, such as volunteering for extra tasks or participating in organizational initiatives, as these activities might have detracted from their ability to meet their familial obligations. Thus, despite the presence of empowering leadership, solo parents might have chosen not to fully participate in contextual performance behaviors due to the perceived misalignment between their personal goals (related to family caregiving) and organizational objectives.

Moreover, Yamamoto and Eto (2019) investigated how leadership styles influence employee work-life balance, comparing Japan and the United States in their study published in the "International Journal of Business and Management". They analyzed how diverse leadership approaches impact employees juggling professional duties with personal and family responsibilities, focusing particularly on challenges faced by solo parents striving to balance caregiving with career advancement. The study revealed that supportive leadership fostered flexibility and understanding, aiding employees managing family obligations, while authoritarian styles often imposed rigid schedules and higher availability expectations, potentially hindering work-life balance.

Subsequently, despite organizational efforts to promote procedural justice in HRM policy implementation, solo parents still perceived a lack of fairness or consistency in how these policies were applied, particularly regarding family-friendly benefits or accommodations. Consequently, Vigoda-Gado and Talmud, (2019) claimed that solo parents might have been less inclined to participate in discretionary behaviors associated with contextual performance, such as volunteering for extra tasks or contributing innovative ideas, as they might have perceived these efforts as undervalued or unfairly rewarded within the organization. Thus, despite organizational efforts to promote procedural justice,

solo parents might have experienced barriers to fully engaging in contextual performance behaviors due to perceived inequities in HRM policy implementation.

The third dimension was counterproductive work behavior. Counterproductive work behavior as defined by Yu (2019) as "voluntary behavior that harmed the well-being of the organization" and included off-task behavior, presentism, complaining, doing tasks incorrectly on purpose, and misusing privileges. CWB was common in the workplace and cost businesses a lot of money each year. CWBs could be small, like taking a pen, or big, like stealing a lot of money from a company. These could happen between people or in an entire organization. Some actions that could harm relationships between employees in an organization were gossip, bullying, and harassment. This meant when people acted in a way that harmed the company they worked for, like skipping work a lot or using company things for their own personal gain. CWB caused harm to companies and groups. It was not unexpected that these actions could seriously harm companies financially.

In support to that, Yu (2019) stated in his journal entitled "The Reality of Counterproductive Work Behaviours" that almost nine (9) out of 10 workers had done things at work that were not helpful or even harmful to the company. Many studies had found that a lot of workers (between 35% and 75%) had confessed to stealing something from their bosses at least one time. This had led to about \$50 billion in losses for American businesses. This number was getting 15% bigger every year.

Additionally, Hogan and Holland (2019) explored personality-job performance relations from a socioanalytic perspective, stating that employees exhibited high levels of conscientiousness, a personality trait characterized by self-discipline, reliability, and a strong work ethic. Individuals high in conscientiousness were less likely to engage in counterproductive behaviors, as they were more diligent in fulfilling their job duties, adhering to organizational rules and norms, and maintaining professionalism in the workplace. Relating it to solo parents, despite the unique challenges faced in balancing work and family responsibilities, they exhibited high levels of conscientiousness in the workplace. Solo parents often developed strong organizational skills, time management abilities, and a sense of responsibility to effectively juggle their caregiving duties with their job roles.

Moreover, Smith (2023) stated that balancing work and family responsibilities can significantly impact single parents' ability to avoid counterproductive behaviors in the workplace. Effective management strategies play a crucial role in mitigating such behaviors. Prioritizing tasks helps single parents focus on essential responsibilities, reducing the likelihood of procrastination or task avoidance. Structured schedules foster organization and consistency, minimizing the risk of absenteeism or tardiness due to childcare conflicts. Utilizing childcare options like nannies or daycare services provides the flexibility needed to maintain job attendance and performance. Similarly, negotiating flexible work arrangements accommodates parental duties without compromising professional obligations, thus decreasing stress and potential burnout. Engaging in self-care activities and seeking support from social networks or support groups also enhances emotional resilience, reducing the probability of workplace conflicts or decreased

productivity. Overall, adopting these strategies facilitates a balanced lifestyle for single parents, fostering workplace efficiency and well-being while mitigating the potential for counterproductive behaviors.

From a different perspective, Reynolds and O'Leary-Kelly (2019) also examined the effect of disorder in the workplace on incivility during selection and recruitment processes. They stated that when employees perceived their work environment as supportive and respectful, they were less likely to engage in counterproductive behaviors, such as absenteeism, theft, or sabotage. Instead, they were motivated to contribute positively to the organization and uphold its values through their actions and behaviors. Solo parents might have experienced a supportive work environment that recognized and accommodated their unique needs and challenges. Organizations that prioritized family-friendly policies, flexible work arrangements, and supportive leadership created an environment where solo parents felt valued and respected.

In such a positive climate, solo parents were less likely to engage in counterproductive behaviors, as they were motivated to reciprocate the support they received from the organization by demonstrating commitment, reliability, and professionalism in their work. Reynolds and O'Leary-Kelly (2019) noted that despite the extra duties confronting solo parents, a workplace culture that offered support could alleviate counterproductive behaviors by nurturing mutual respect, trust, and gratitude between the organization and its workforce.

Relationship between Solo Parent Awareness of R.A. 8972 and Work Performance

Republic Act 8972, also known as the Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000, provided benefits and privileges to solo parents in the Philippines, recognizing their rights and supporting them in fulfilling their responsibilities. When considering its relationship with work performance, Pena and Rivas (2019) revealed in their study titled "Effects of Republic Act No. 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) on the Work Performance of Solo Parents in Muntinlupa City," that several significant impacts of RA 8972 on the work performance of solo parents in Muntinlupa City. Firstly, the legislation contributed to enhancing employment stability among solo parents, providing them with a safety net and support system, thereby reducing the risk of job insecurity. Secondly, the study highlighted improvements in productivity among solo parents, as the benefits and privileges afforded by the act enabled them to better focus on their work responsibilities without the burden of excessive stressors related to their family situation.

Moreover, Pena and Rivas's (2019) research shed light on the positive effects of RA 8972 on promoting work-life balance among solo parents. By offering support in terms of childcare assistance, flexible work arrangements, and access to welfare programs, the act facilitated a more harmonious integration of work and family duties for solo parents in Muntinlupa City. The study provided valuable insights into how the implementation of RA 8972 positively influenced the work performance of solo parents in Muntinlupa City, Philippines, by fostering employment stability, productivity, and work-life balance.

On another key point, Roxas et al. (2019) delved into the effects of RA 8972 on work-life balance and job performance among government employees who were solo parents in the City of San Fernando, Pampanga. Their research aimed to understand the perceptions of solo parents regarding the support provided by the law and its influence on their work performance. Their findings shed light on the multifaceted impact of RA 8972 on solo parents employed in government positions in San Fernando, Pampanga. Firstly, the study revealed that the provisions of the law played a significant role in improving work-life balance for solo parents, as it provided them with access to various benefits and support systems, such as flexible work arrangements and childcare assistance. These provisions allowed solo parents to better manage their family responsibilities alongside their job commitments, thereby fostering a more harmonious integration of work and personal life.

Secondly, the research highlighted the positive influence of RA 8972 on job performance among solo parents. By alleviating some of the stressors associated with single parenthood through the support provided by the law, such as financial assistance and social welfare programs, solo parents were able to focus more effectively on their work responsibilities. This, in turn, led to enhanced job performance and productivity among government employees who were solo parents in San Fernando, Pampanga.

By offering support tailored to the needs of solo parents, the law contributed to creating a conducive work environment that enabled solo parents to thrive both personally and professionally.

Synthesis

The literature review highlighted the complex landscape of single parenthood, drawing insights from various sources including academic research, legal frameworks, and community initiatives.

As indicated in the studies of Zuckerman (2020), Kluch & Crabtree (2020), and Alngag (2022), a comprehensive demographic analysis provided statistical evidence of the prevalence of single-parent households. Additionally, they shed light on the economic challenges faced by single mothers worldwide, including struggles with food insecurity and housing affordability, and emphasized the wide range of responsibilities single parents undertook, including tending to their children's health and emotional well-being.

Furthermore, in workplace challenges and legal awareness, Maldonado and Nieuwenhuis (2019), Schulte and Pabst (2021), Lee (2021), Castaneda (2021), Gilmore, 2021, Moss (2021) and (Yost, 2021 highlighted workplace challenges encountered by single parents, including discrimination and inadequate support, underscore the need for systemic changes in work culture to accommodate their needs by advocating for policies that facilitate single parents' access to the labor market and promote work-life balance.

In the realm of community and government support, the works of Ramirez (2019), Tan (2022), Tan and Lim (2020), Gonzales et al. (2021), and Dela Cruz, Yap, Kung, &

Ching, 2023, Single Parent Rights (2024), Reyes (2022) , United Nations Development Programme Annual Report (2023), pandan-antique.gov.ph (2023) and Pew Research Center (2022) underscore the critical role of initiatives like Solo Parent's Week and orientation programs in enhancing awareness and providing essential resources across the Philippines. These efforts not only improve financial stability and educational opportunities for single-parent households but also contribute to their overall well-being and resilience within the community. Addressing resource limitations in local governance remains crucial to ensuring adequate provision of services such as childcare facilities and infrastructure improvements, essential for supporting the holistic needs of single-parent households.

Importantly, Santos (2021), Keum (2023), Stack & Meredith (2019), Sharma and Singh (2020), Horák, F., Lacko, D., & Klocek, A. (2021), and Legerde (2023) also emphasized the efforts to disseminate information about the Solo Parent Act through government agencies, media, and community organizations enhance solo parents' legal consciousness, enabling better access to their entitlements. Media representations and research on language barriers in legal access underscore societal attitudes, systemic challenges, and cultural dynamics affecting solo parents, providing insights into their experiences and areas for supportive intervention.

Also worth mentioning was the research conducted by Rotundo and Sackett (2022), Gunyakti, A, et al.(2024), Hetland (2022), Meier et al. (2019), Brewer and Chen (2020), Li et al. (2020). Bhardwaj & Kalia (2021), Nini (2019), Lam and Liang (2019), Yamamoto & Eto (2019), Vigoda-Gado & Talmud (2019), Yu (2019), Hogan and Holland (2019), Smith (2023) and Reynolds & O'Leary-Kelly (2019) which explored the three domains of work performance, the studies highlighted the importance of task performance for organizational success, noting the unique challenges faced by solo parents. They emphasized also that empowering leadership could alleviate stress related to task performance, particularly for solo parents, and stressed the significance of supportive organizational cultures. Moreover, they discussed how contextual performance and counterproductive work behaviors posed challenges for solo parents balancing work and family responsibilities, underscoring the need for supportive work environments to mitigate these issues effectively.

To highlight, Pena and Rivas (2019) and Roxas et al. (2019) found that the act's provisions, including childcare support and flexible work arrangements, facilitated better integration of work and family responsibilities, fostering a more harmonious work-life balance. The law's support mechanisms alleviated stressors, enabling solo parents to focus more effectively on their work duties and contributing to enhanced productivity and job satisfaction.

Despite these insights, the awareness of RA 8972 among solo parents in private companies remains underexplored. Understanding its implications on job performance is critical, this research aimed to fill this gap by examining the impact of RA 8972 awareness on performance within XYZ Corporation, shedding light on factors affecting its implementation and contributing to broader discussions on supporting solo parents in the

workplace. The majority of the research focuses only on the social interventions available to help solo parents both working and studying. The need to research this topic is particularly pressing today, as Solo Parents are increasing and every company needs to know that they exist. This study will impact on the awareness of solo parent, the extent of implementation, and the degree of seriousness of the factors that affect the implementation of the Solo Parent Welfare Act of 2000 that private companies specific to XYZ Corporation had contributed directly or indirectly.

The study addressed a gap in the existing research by investigating the relationship between solo parent employees' awareness of Republic Act 8972 (RA 8972) and their work performance within the context of XYZ Corporation. At the time of the study, there was limited empirical research specifically examining the awareness levels of solo parent employees regarding their rights and benefits under RA 8972 and how this awareness influenced their performance in the workplace, particularly within the setting of XYZ Corporation.

Prior studies on solo parenthood and work performance predominantly focused on broader demographic groups or explored the effects of work-life balance initiatives without specifically delving into the awareness and utilization of legal protections provided by RA 8972. Furthermore, while some research had explored the implementation of RA 8972 at the national level, there was a noticeable gap in studies investigating its application within specific corporate environments, such as XYZ Corporation.

The study aimed to bridge this gap by conducting a comprehensive examination of solo parent employees' awareness levels regarding RA 8972 within XYZ Corporation and investigating the relationship between this awareness and various indicators of work performance. By filling this literature gap, the study sought to contribute to a deeper understanding of the role of legal awareness in shaping the experiences and outcomes of solo parent employees in the workplace. The findings were anticipated to inform human resources policies and practices aimed at supporting this demographic group and enhancing overall organizational performance in the past.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational method of research was used in determining the relationship between solo parent employees' awareness of RA 8972 as an independent variable and the level of work performance as the dependent variable. The descriptive analysis was applied as the study described the current status of an identified variable; together with correlational analysis, it attempted to evaluate the extent of a relationship between variables by using statistical data.

The purpose of a descriptive correlational research design according to Babbie (2019) was to examine the relationship between two or more variables without

manipulating them. Instead of seeking to establish cause-and-effect relationships, this type of research aimed to describe and understand the degree to which variables were related or associated with each other. Descriptive correlational studies provided valuable insights into patterns, trends, and connections between variables in a natural setting.

Research Locale

The research was conducted on the solo parents employed in XYZ Corporation located in Cebu, Davao, and Laguna, who were working across various departments within the manufacturing firm. This includes direct employees of any age and gender who qualify as solo parents.

Population and Sampling

This study used purposeful sampling. Purposeful selection was a non-probabilistic sampling technique used in qualitative research. Saldana (2021) stated that unlike probabilistic sampling methods that rely on random selection, purposeful sampling involved deliberately selecting participants or cases based on specific criteria that were relevant to the research objectives.

In this instance, the focus of the study was on solo parents within XYZ Corporation, a manufacturing company with a total workforce of 670 employees spread across three locations: Laguna, Davao, and the main branch in Cebu. Out of this total workforce, there were 59 solo parents identified. These solo parents, constituting a subset of the larger employee population, were specifically selected as the target respondents for the research study.

Respondents of the Study

Table A

Respondents of the Study

Location	Number of Solo Parent	Gender	
		Male	Female
Cebu	15	7	8
Davao	9	1	8
Laguna	35	13	22
TOTAL	59	21	38

The study encompassed a diverse pool of respondents, totaling 59 solo parents, comprising 21 males and 38 females. These individuals were drawn from different offices within the organization, with 15 solo parents located in the Cebu Office, 9 in the Davao Office, and the largest contingent of 35 solo parents situated in the Laguna Office.

Instrument

The questionnaires used in this quantitative research were adapted from the previous study conducted by Cornelio et al. (2013) entitled “The government’s support for solo parent’s in Brgy. La Carlota”. The questionnaire was also modified to make it more suitable for the proponents of this study. As for job performance, the brief self-report scale of the individual work performance questionnaire was also reformed and adjusted to appropriately measure solo parents’ job performance.

The four-point Likert was also used to produce replies and evaluate the quantitative value of the dimension being evaluated. The use of the Likert scale in this study was further clarified by the researcher, with an interpretation presented below.

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees in XYZ Corporation o RA 8972

Range	Rating	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	4	Fully Aware
2.50 – 3.24	3	Aware
1.75 – 2.49	2	Partially Aware
1.00 – 1.74	1	Not Aware

Mean-score Interval and Verbal Interpretation on the Level of Work Performance of Solo Parent Employees

Range	Rating	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
3.25 – 4.00	4	Always	Very Good
2.50 – 3.24	3	Often	Good
1.75 – 2.49	2	Seldom	Fair
1.00 – 1.74	1	Never	Poor

Validation of the Instrument

To be assured of the appropriateness of the survey, though it was a standardized questionnaire, it was still presented for approval by the experts and the people in authority in research and statistics. The survey questionnaire also underwent reliability testing to check its clarity, comprehensibility, and acceptability before it was distributed to the target respondents.

Based on the calculated Lawshe Content Validity Ratio, the instrument was found to meet the satisfactory threshold of 1.0. Therefore, the questionnaire scale achieved a acceptable level of content validity.

The instrument underwent pilot testing with 23 solo parent employees who were not part of the main respondent group. Cronbach's Alpha was employed to assess the instrument's internal reliability and consistency. Validation of the instrument was conducted by experts, including the researcher's statistician, an LCBA professor, and a human resource specialist in this domain. These experts ensured that all pertinent research considerations were addressed and clarified.

Data Gathering Procedure

Following the acceptance of the thesis proposal, authorization from the Dean of the Graduate School was obtained. Subsequently, a formal letter was drafted and directed to the Organizational Development Manager and the President of XYZ Company, along with letters addressed to the prospective respondents. With the help of the Human Resources department and the respondents a questionnaire assessment was conducted. The time of the study was conducted on the break time of the employees and sometimes was informally scheduled depending on their availability. The traditional method of conducting a questionnaire survey was used in collecting the data.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The following statistical treatments were employed:

1. The Mean and Four-point Likert scale were employed to describe the level of awareness of Solo Parent Employees in XYZ Corporation to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and their level of work performance.

2. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to show the relationship between the Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and their level of work performance. The correlation was used since the relationship between two variables has a significant effect ($P > .05$).

RESULTS

This chapter provides a detailed analysis and interpretation of the data gathered to address the research questions outlined in the study. The discussion follows the sequence of the problem statements laid out in the introductory chapter. In doing so, it aims to systematically explore and provide insights into the issues raised, offering a coherent understanding of the research findings within the context of the study's objectives.

Research Question 1: What is the level of awareness of solo parent employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) in XYZ Corporation as assessed by employees in terms of:

1.1 Legal Literacy

Table 1.1

Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) in XYZ Corporation as assessed by Employees in terms of Legal Literacy (Legal Definition of Solo Parent)

Indicators in terms of Legal Literacy	$\bar{X}$	VI	Rank
1. A woman who gives birth as a result of rape and other crimes against chastity even without a final conviction of the offender. Provided, that the mother keeps and raises the child.	3.75	FA	8
2. A parent left solo or alone with the responsibility of parenthood due to the death of a spouse.	3.73	FA	9
3. A parent left solo or alone with the responsibility of parenthood while the spouse is detained or is serving a sentence for a criminal conviction for at least one (1) year.	3.76	FA	6.5
4. A parent left solo or alone with the responsibility of parenthood due to physical and/or mental incapacity of spouse as certified by a public medical practitioner.	3.83	FA	3
5. A parent left solo or alone with the responsibility of parenthood due to legal separation or de facto separation from spouse for at least one (1) year as long as he/she is entrusted with the custody of the children.	3.81	FA	4.5
6. A parent left solo or alone with the responsibility of parenthood due to a declaration of nullity or annulment of marriage as decreed by a court or by a church as long as he/she is entrusted with the custody of the children.	3.69	FA	10
7. A parent left solo or alone with the responsibility of parenthood due to abandonment of spouse for at least (1) year.	3.81	FA	4.5
8. An unmarried mother/father who has preferred to keep and rear her/his child/ children instead of having others care for them or give them up to a welfare institution.	3.86	FA	1
9. Any other person who solely provides parental care and support to a child or children.	3.76	FA	6.5
10. Any family member who assumes the responsibility of the head of the family as a result of death, abandonment, disappearance, or prolonged absence of the parents or solo parent.	3.85	FA	2
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.79	FA	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Fully Aware (FA)
2.50 – 3.24 Aware (A)

1.75 – 2.49 Partially Aware (PA)
1.00 – 1.74 Not Aware (NA)

Solo Parent Employees were **Fully Aware (3.79)** of the **Legal Literacy** of RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000). All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Aware**. Furthermore, the indicator "An unmarried mother/father who has preferred to keep and rear her/his child/ children instead of having others care for them or give them up to a welfare institution." had the highest computed mean of **3.86** meanwhile, the indicator "A parent left solo or alone with the responsibility of parenthood due to a declaration of nullity or annulment of marriage as decreed by a court or by a church as

long as he/she is entrusted with the custody of the children” had the lowest computed mean of **3.69**.

1.2 Benefits and Privileges

Table 1.2

Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents’ Welfare Act of 2000) in XYZ Corporation as assessed by Employees in terms of Benefits and Privileges

Indicators in terms of Benefits and Privileges	$\bar{X}$	VI	Rank
1. Livelihood development services.	1.24	NA	9.5
2. Counseling services.	1.56	NA	2
3. Parent effectiveness services.	1.31	NA	6
4. Critical incidence stress debriefing.	1.27	NA	7
5. Special projects for individuals in need of protection.	1.25	NA	8
6. Flexible work schedule.	1.47	NA	4
7. Work Discrimination.	1.98	PA	1
8. Parental Leave.	1.41	NA	5
9. Educational Benefit.	1.51	NA	3
10. Housing Benefits.	1.22	NA	11
11. Medical Assistance.	1.24	NA	9.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	1.41	NA	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Fully Aware (FA)
2.50 – 3.24 Aware (A)

1.75 – 2.49 Partially Aware (PA)
1.00 – 1.74 Not Aware (NA)

Solo Parent Employees were **Not Aware (1.41)** of the **Benefits and Privileges** of RA 8972 (Solo Parents’ Welfare Act of 2000). Furthermore, the indicator “Work Discrimination. No employer shall discriminate against any solo parent employee with respect to terms and conditions of employment on account of his/her status.” had the highest computed mean of **1.98** verbally interpreted as **Partially Aware**. Meanwhile, the indicator “Housing Benefits. Solo parents shall be given allocation in housing projects and shall be provided with liberal terms of payment on said government low-cost housing projects in accordance with housing law provisions prioritizing applicants below the poverty line as declared by the NEDA.” had the lowest computed mean of **1.22** verbally interpreted as **Not Aware**.

GENERAL ASSESSMENT		2.49	F
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very Good (VG)	1.75 – 2.49 Fair (F)		
2.50 – 3.24 Good (G)	1.00 – 1.74 Poor (P)		

XYZ Corporation’s Solo Parent employees’ **Contextual Performance** was **Fair (2.49)**. Furthermore, the indicator “Start new task when old task were completed.” had the highest computed mean of **3.20** verbally interpreted as **Good**. Meanwhile, the indicator “Actively participate in meetings and/or consultations to contribute effectively to the organization’s success.” had the lowest computed mean of **1.78** verbally interpreted as **Fair**.

2.3 Counterproductive Behaviour

Table 2.3

Level of Work Performance of Solo Parent Employees in XYZ Corporation as assessed by the Solo Parent Employees in terms of Counterproductive Behavior

Indicators in terms of Counterproductive Behavior	$\bar{X}$	VI	Rank
As an employee, I...			
1. Complain about minor work-related issues	1.20	P	1
2. Make problems at work bigger than they were	1.17	P	2
3. Focus on the negative aspects of situation at work instead of the positive aspects	1.02	P	3
4. Talk to colleagues about negative aspect of work	1.00	P	4.5
5. Talk to people outside the organization about negative aspect of work	1.00	P	4.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	1.08	P	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Very Good (VG)	1.75 – 2.49 Fair (F)
2.50 – 3.24 Good (G)	1.00 – 1.74 Poor (P)

XYZ Corporation’s Solo Parent employees’ **Counterproductive Behavior** was **Poor (1.08)**. Furthermore, the indicator “Complain about minor work-related issues” had the highest computed mean of **1.20** verbally interpreted as **Poor**. Meanwhile, the indicator “Talk to colleagues about the negative aspect of work.” and “Talk to people outside the organization about the negative aspect of work” had the lowest computed mean of **1.00** verbally interpreted as **Poor**.

Research Question 3: Is there a significant relationship between the Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and Work Performance of employees working in XYZ Corporation?

Table 3

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and Work Performance of Employees Working in XYZ Corporation

Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972	Work Performance	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Legal Literacy	Task Performance	.022	.872	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Contextual Performance	.174	.187	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Counterproductive Behavior	.231	.078	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
Benefits and Privileges	Task Performance	.104	.431	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Contextual Performance	.208	.115	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
	Counterproductive Behavior	.216	.101	Not Significant	Accept H ₀
Factors that affect the implementation of this Act	Task Performance	.315*	.015	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Contextual Performance	.267*	.041	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Counterproductive Behavior	.164*	.045	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

There was a significant relationship between the level of awareness of solo parent employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and the work performance of solo parent employees working in XYZ Corporation. The r values .164 to .315 were interpreted as with a low positive correlation as to correlate Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 in terms of Factors that affect the implementation of this Act and Work Performance. The computed probability values .015, .041, and .045 were lesser than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Research Question 4: Based on the results of the study, what action plan can be proposed to further improve the Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and the Work Performance of employees working in XYZ Corporation?

A Solo Parent Awareness Enhancement Program has been proposed as a strategic initiative aimed at assisting XYZ Corporation in fostering a supportive and inclusive environment for solo parent employees, ultimately enhancing their work performance and overall well-being. Recognizing the significance of RA 8972 (Solo Parent Welfare Act), these programs are designed to address the various challenges

faced by solo parents in the workplace. By implementing these proposals, XYZ Corporation not only demonstrates its commitment to supporting its solo parent workforce but also aligns with the provisions of RA 8972, thereby contributing to the success and fulfillment of its employees.

Table 4

Proposed Action Plan to further Enhance the Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and Work Performance

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies	Time Frame	Person Involved	Source of Funds	Success Indicator
Awareness of Solo parent to RA 8972's Benefits & Privileges	To provide visual cues that will serve as reminders and prompts for employees to familiarize themselves with the Act and stay informed about their rights and entitlements	Enhancement of Communication and Information dissemination strategies. a) Establishing clear communication channels within the organization b) Leverage the company's intranet portal and provide a centralized platform for sharing updates.	Oct 2024	Human Resource Specialist Information Technology Specialist	Additional Budget-Actual cost of supplies that will be used in displaying information & Investment cost for the update of HRIS for the intranet portal.	90-95% of visual cues are in place before the end of the year.
Awareness of Solo parent to the factors that affects the implementation of RA8972	To sustain awareness of Solo Parent by conducting collaborations with Govt. Agency.	Company's Initiative and Collaboration with Government Agencies. Establish partnerships with relevant government agencies such as the DSWD and	Oct 2024	Org. Development Manager	Additional Budget-Actual cost of Training and Honorarium for Guest Speaker.	90-100% of solo parents sustained awareness.

		DOLE, as well as NGOs specializing in solo parent welfare like the Solo Parents Welfare Act Association of the Philippines (SPWAP).		/ Top Mngt		
Contextual Performance used to measure work performance	-To develop Solo Parent employees to have the ability to generate innovative and creative solutions for new problems & strengthen communication, collab, and leadership skills to actively participate in meetings and consultations.	Enhancement of Training and Skill Development for solo parent Offer training sessions or workshops specifically focused on enhancing communication and participation skills for solo parent employees. <i>(Covering effective communication techniques, active listening skills, and strategies for confidently contributing ideas and insights during meetings)</i>	Oct 2024	Technical Training Manager	Additional- Actual cost of Training and Honorarium for Guest Speaker.	90% - 100% employees developed creative traits and work engagement.

DISCUSSION

From the data gathered and analyzed, the following findings were:

1. Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000 as assessed by Employees in terms of:

1.1 Legal Literacy

It had a general assessment of **3.79** verbally interpreted as **Fully Aware**.

The results imply that one significant factor was the widespread dissemination of information about the law through government agencies, media channels, community organizations, and advocacy groups. Additionally, the Solo Parent Act addressed an important social issue in the Philippines, which may have garnered significant attention and discussion among the general populace.

Moreover, the provisions of the law directly impacted a substantial portion of the population, as many Filipinos were either solo parents themselves or had family members or acquaintances who were solo parents, leading to increased awareness and interest in the Act. One program used to spread awareness was the Solo Parent's Week, which was indeed observed annually in the Philippines. It typically took place during the second week of September. This event aimed to raise awareness about the rights and challenges faced by solo parents in the country. During Solo Parent's Week, various activities, seminars, and programs were organized by government agencies, non-profit organizations, and community groups to provide support, information, and assistance to solo parents. The goal was to recognize their contributions to society and promote understanding and empathy toward their situations (dswd.gov.ph).

Furthermore, some private sector employers actively collaborated with DSWD in informing their employees about the provisions of RA 8972 and the benefits available to solo parents. This was through employee orientation programs, company newsletters, or dedicated information sessions. On February 23, 2023, at the Liberman Sports Complex in Pandan, Antique, the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) Field Office–Antique, in collaboration with the Pandan Municipal Social Welfare and Development Office (MSWDO) under the direction of Ms. Mary Ann A. Samulde, hosted an orientation on RA 8972. For them to utilize their rights and benefits, 407 single parents received orientation, and the legal definition of “solo parent” was discussed as well (Pandan-antique.gov.ph).

1.2 Benefits and Privileges

It had a general assessment of **1.41** verbally interpreted as **Not Aware**.

This lack of awareness may stem from various factors such as limited access to information, language barriers, and low literacy levels. These challenges hindered effective communication and understanding of their rights under RA 8972.

Based on Santos's (2021) study, which examined how media advocacy and public discourse influence the implementation of the Solo Parents' Welfare Act to increase awareness and comprehension of the benefits outlined in RA 8972, it was found that despite the requirement for solo parents to participate in orientations or seminars organized by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) or accredited local entities, many employed solo parents still remained unaware of their entitlements due to limited access to information and language barriers, highlighting persistent challenges in ensuring broad awareness and effective utilization of the law's provisions.

Moreover, Dela Cruz and Reyes (2022) conducted a thorough analysis of RA 11861's overall efficacy in Zamboanga City, evaluating the degree of accessibility, utilization, and satisfaction single parents had with the legal advantages and services. The research highlighted areas requiring improvement, such as raising awareness and expediting application procedures, to ensure targeted assistance efficiently reached all eligible single-parent homes. R.A. 11861, also known as the "Expanded Solo Parents Welfare Act," modified R.A. 8972, the "Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000," to provide extra assistance and privileges to solo parents, aligning with the state's commitment to advancing social justice.

Furthermore, according to Keum (2023), solo parents, particularly those residing in marginalized or remote areas, faced challenges accessing resources like internet connectivity, printed materials, or community outreach programs aimed at disseminating information about their entitlements under the law. Additionally, language barriers and low literacy levels could have further complicated their ability to comprehend information about their rights under RA 8972, hindering effective communication and understanding of legal documents or government announcements.

1.3 Factors that Affect the Implementation of this Act

It had a general assessment of **2.09** verbally interpreted as **Partially Aware**.

The result may be attributed to several factors: Firstly, there was a general lack of awareness among communities regarding legal rights and welfare acts due to the lack of formal seminars on the Solo Parent Welfare Act of 2000 (RA 8972) conducted by the Barangay Development Council. Secondly, is due to resource constraints that significantly impact local authorities' ability to prioritize initiatives like the Solo Parent Welfare Act. Financial limitations, inadequate human resources, and infrastructure deficiencies contribute to these challenges.

Specifically, studies on community awareness of legal provisions and welfare acts often revealed significant gaps in understanding among the general population. For instance, Sharma and Singh (2020) found that rural communities in India frequently

lacked awareness of their legal rights and protections, underscoring the importance of effective legal frameworks in empowering marginalized populations. This insight was crucial for assessing solo parents' comprehension of their legal rights, including basic concepts like labor rights and social welfare entitlements, which may explain why these issues are not prioritized in community agendas.

Furthermore, resource constraints posed significant challenges for local authorities, affecting their ability to prioritize initiatives such as the Solo Parent Welfare Act. According to reports from the United Nations Development Programme (Annual Report, 2023), local governments often faced financial limitations due to constrained budgets, inadequate revenue sources, and competing expenditure priorities. Moreover, many struggle with human resource shortages, particularly in rural areas, which hindered effective governance. Infrastructure deficiencies further compound these challenges, impacting service delivery and quality of life, including solo parents.

Additionally, community surveys conducted by local governments and NGOs reveal that other priorities, such as infrastructure development, public health, education, economic growth, environmental protection, and disaster management, often take precedence over addressing solo parent rights. For instance, Pew Research Center (2022) reports indicated that strengthening the economy ranks significantly higher in public policy priorities compared to social welfare issues like drug addiction.

2. Level of Work Performance of Solo Parent Employees in XYZ Corporation as assessed by the Solo Parent Employees in terms of:

2.1 Task Performance

It had a general assessment of **3.89** verbally interpreted as **Very Good**.

The implication of achieving a "very good" rating in task performance underscores the manifestation of structured goal-setting, clear communication, and effective team coordination. Such ratings indicate a high level of satisfaction and success in completing tasks efficiently and effectively. They reflect not only the capability and commitment of team members but also their ability to exceed expectations in terms of quality, accuracy, and attention to detail. This highlights the critical role of robust task management practices in consistently delivering high-quality outputs within constraints of time and resources.

Referencing the findings of the study by Brewer and Chen (2020), it could be argued that task performance was at a "very good" level because individuals' personal values played a significant role in shaping their attitudes, behaviors, and outcomes in the workplace. When personal values were closely aligned with task objectives, it fostered a conducive environment for high levels of performance, commitment, and satisfaction among employees. Additionally, when solo parents believed that their work was meaningful and resonated with their core values, they were likely to approach tasks with greater enthusiasm, dedication, and effectiveness. Personal values often served as

sources of intrinsic motivation, driving individuals to excel in their work and contribute meaningfully to organizational goals.

The study by Li et al. (2020) found that empowering leadership style encouraged employees to take ownership of their tasks and provided them with autonomy in decision-making. When employees felt empowered to make meaningful contributions and exercised discretion in how they approached their work, they were more likely to demonstrate high levels of task performance. It was also revealed that empowering leadership was associated with promoting a supportive work environment that valued work-life balance. Leaders who demonstrated understanding and flexibility regarding employees' family commitments and personal needs created a positive organizational culture that fostered employee well-being. Similarly, with the situation of the majority of solo parents, when they felt supported in managing their work and family responsibilities, they were better able to focus on their tasks and perform at a high level.

2.2 Contextual Performance

It had a general assessment of **2.49** verbally interpreted as **Fair**.

It suggests that solo parent employees are not actively engaging in these discretionary behaviors. Solo parents may be less inclined to engage in contextual performance behaviors despite organizational efforts to foster empowerment. Solo parents often prioritize family well-being and caregiving responsibilities over career advancement, which may lead them to perceive contextual performance tasks—such as volunteering for extra responsibilities or contributing innovative ideas—as conflicting with their primary familial goals. This perceived misalignment between personal and organizational objectives could potentially deter solo parents from fully participating in discretionary behaviors associated with contextual performance.

Based on the study by Lam and Liang (2019), which explored how empowering leadership influenced employee voice behavior, a hypothetical reason why contextual performance might have received a general assessment indicating disagreement could have been a misalignment of employee goals with organizational objectives. The research findings suggested that despite the presence of empowering leadership, there was a misalignment between employees' personal goals and the broader organizational objectives. While empowering leadership encouraged voice behavior by creating opportunities for employees to contribute ideas and suggestions, employees might not have perceived these behaviors as contributing to their personal goals or career advancement within the organization. As a result, they might have chosen not to engage in discretionary behaviors associated with contextual performance, such as offering suggestions for improvement or taking on additional tasks beyond their formal job roles.

While empowering leadership encouraged voice behavior and offered opportunities for employees to contribute ideas and suggestions, solo parents might have perceived these behaviors as conflicting with their primary goal of balancing work and family responsibilities. Yamamoto and Eto (2019) stated that in many cases, solo parents

prioritized their family's well-being and the need to fulfill caregiving responsibilities over career advancement within the organization. As a result, they might have been less inclined to engage in discretionary behaviors associated with contextual performance, such as volunteering for extra tasks or participating in organizational initiatives, as these activities could have detracted from their ability to meet their familial obligations. Thus, despite the presence of empowering leadership, solo parents might have chosen not to fully participate in contextual performance behaviors due to the perceived misalignment between their personal goals (related to family caregiving) and organizational objectives.

Furthermore, despite organizational attempts to foster procedural justice in HRM policy implementation, solo parents might have perceived inconsistencies or unfairness in how these policies were enacted, especially concerning family-friendly benefits or accommodations according to Vigoda-Gado and Talmud, (2019). They might have believed that HRM policies related to flexible work arrangements, parental leave, or childcare support were not adequately applied or favored employees without caregiving responsibilities. This perception of procedural injustice could have worsened the struggles solo parents faced in managing work and family duties, resulting in frustration, stress, and decreased engagement.

Consequently, Vigoda-Gadot and Talmud (2019) also stated that solo parents might have been less inclined to participate in discretionary behaviors associated with contextual performance, as they might have perceived these efforts as undervalued or unfairly rewarded within the organization. Thus, despite organizational efforts to promote procedural justice, solo parents might have experienced barriers to fully engaging in contextual performance behaviors due to perceived inequities in HRM policy implementation.

2.3 Counterproductive Behavior

It had a general assessment of **1.20** verbally interpreted as **Poor**.

It implies that solo parents have a strong commitment to professionalism, job performance, collaboration, and organizational values. They prioritize and maintain positive work relationships, avoid conflict, and contribute positively to the overall success of the organization.

Highlighted here, Hogan and Holland (2019) explored personality-job performance relations from a socioanalytic perspective. A hypothetical reason why counterproductive behavior might have received a general assessment indicating strong disagreement could be due to high levels of conscientiousness among employees. The study suggested that employees exhibited high levels of conscientiousness, a personality trait characterized by self-discipline, reliability, and a strong work ethic. Individuals high in conscientiousness were less likely to engage in counterproductive behaviors, as they were more diligent in fulfilling their job duties, adhering to organizational rules and norms, and maintaining professionalism in the workplace.

Drawing a parallel to solo parents, despite the unique challenges they faced in balancing work and family responsibilities, they may have exhibited high levels of conscientiousness in the workplace. Smith (2023) stated that solo parents often developed strong organizational skills, time management abilities, and a sense of responsibility to effectively juggle their caregiving duties with their job roles. As a result, solo parents were less likely to engage in counterproductive behaviors, such as absenteeism, tardiness, or workplace conflicts, as they prioritized meeting their job requirements and maintaining professionalism in their work.

In contrast, Reynolds and O'Leary-Kelly (2019) examined the effect of disorder in the workplace on incivility during selection and recruitment processes. A hypothetical reason why counterproductive behavior might have received a general assessment indicating strong disagreement could have been a positive organizational climate and culture. Organizations fostered a positive climate and culture characterized by respect, collaboration, and professionalism. When employees perceived their work environment as supportive and respectful, they were less likely to engage in counterproductive behaviors, such as absenteeism, theft, or sabotage. Instead, they were motivated to contribute positively to the organization and uphold its values through their actions and behaviors.

Furthermore, Reynolds and O'Leary-Kelly (2019) stated that despite the additional responsibilities faced by solo parents, a supportive work environment could mitigate the occurrence of counterproductive behaviors by fostering a sense of mutual respect, trust, and appreciation between the organization and its employees. Therefore, a strongly disagreeing assessment of counterproductive behavior among solo parents could imply that they perceived their work environment as conducive to positive and productive behavior, leading to minimal instances of counterproductive behavior.

3. Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and the Level of Work Performance of Solo Parent Employees in XYZ Corporation as assessed by the Solo Parent Employees

Each factor that affected the implementation of RA 8972 (Solo Parent Welfare Act of 2000) could have influenced the awareness of solo parent employees and subsequently impacted their work performance. The lack of local support groups, as indicated by the Health Encyclopedia (2024) meant that solo parents might not have had access to resources, information, or networks that could have enhanced their awareness of RA 8972 and the services available to them. Without support groups, solo parents might have felt isolated and unaware of their rights and entitlements under the law, leading to lower awareness levels. Lower awareness could have resulted in solo parents being less informed about the support services and benefits they were entitled to, potentially impacting their ability to balance work and family responsibilities effectively.

If the Solo Parent Welfare Act was not considered a priority issue in the community, it was less likely that awareness-raising efforts, such as formal seminars conducted by

Barangay Development Councils, would have been organized. Alngag (2022) stated that without formal seminars or educational initiatives, solo parents might have remained unaware of their rights and the support available to them under RA 8972, leading to lower awareness levels. Limited community focus on solo parent issues might have contributed to a lack of visibility and understanding of the challenges faced by solo parents, further hindering awareness and support efforts.

Furthermore, the lack of comprehensive support services and benefits provided by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) could have also contributed to lower awareness levels among solo parents. Solo parents might not have felt the impact of RA 8972 if they did not have access to essential services such as livelihood support, skills development, educational assistance, and health services. Alngag (2022) also stated that without tangible support from government agencies like DSWD, solo parents might have perceived RA 8972 as ineffective or irrelevant to their needs, leading to decreased awareness and engagement with the law.

Additionally, conservative attitudes within the community towards single parenthood created stigma and discrimination against solo parents, making them hesitant to seek information or support related to RA 8972. Fear of judgment or social exclusion might have discouraged solo parents from actively engaging in awareness-raising initiatives or seeking assistance from local authorities or support groups. Limited community support and acceptance could have contributed to solo parents feeling marginalized and isolated, affecting their awareness levels and overall well-being (singleparentrights, 2024).

Lastly, a lack of awareness among Barangay Development Council members could have resulted in missed opportunities for collaboration with government agencies, NGOs, and other stakeholders to raise awareness and implement support programs for solo parents. Without active involvement from local authorities and community leaders, solo parents might have had limited access to accurate information and support services, impacting their awareness levels and ability to navigate their rights under RA 8972 (Philippine Commission on Women, 2023)

4. Proposed Action Plan

The establishment of a proposed action plan or program awareness was undertaken to further enhance the Level of Awareness of Solo Parent Employees to RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) and their level of Work Performance. This includes Improvement of Comprehensive training programs, Enhancement of Communication and Information dissemination strategies, creating a policy prioritizing transparency and accessibility on the supportive measures for solo parents, company's initiative and collaboration with government agencies and enhancement of training and skill development for solo parent.

Conclusions

Based on the above-mentioned findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. That the Solo Parent employees demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of the legal definition of Solo Parent as outlined in RA 8972 (Solo Parents' Welfare Act of 2000) in XYZ Corporation, as evidenced by the high level of awareness can be attributed to several key factors such as widespread dissemination efforts through government agencies, media channels, community organizations, and advocacy groups played a crucial role in educating the public about the Solo Parents' Welfare Act. Conversely, solo parent employees exhibited a lower level of awareness regarding the benefits and privileges stipulated in RA 8972. This lack of awareness is attributed due to limited access to information, language barriers, and low literacy levels among solo parents. Despite initiatives requiring their participation in orientations or seminars, many solo parents faced difficulties comprehending their entitlements due to these barriers, indicating a need for more accessible and inclusive information dissemination strategies. The partial awareness of factors influencing the implementation of RA 8972 among solo parent employees reflects broader community challenges. Specifically, the absence of formal seminars conducted by Barangay Development Councils on the Solo Parent Welfare Act and resource constraints faced by local authorities contribute significantly to this outcome.

2. That the Task performance ratings among solo parent employees at XYZ Corporation highlight their exceptional capabilities in structured goal-setting, effective communication, and coordinated teamwork. These ratings reflect a high level of satisfaction and success in delivering tasks with precision, quality, and attention to detail, underscoring their commitment and competence. This can be attributed to the alignment of personal values with task objectives, which motivates solo parents to approach their work with enthusiasm and dedication. Conversely, with regard to contextual performance it indicates that solo parents may be less inclined to engage in discretionary behaviors such as contributing innovative ideas or taking on additional responsibilities. This reluctance could stem from perceived misalignments between personal and organizational goals, that despite organizational efforts, solo parents prioritize family well-being over career advancement, potentially impacting their engagement in contextual performance tasks. Furthermore, the minimal incidence of counterproductive behavior among solo parents, underscores their strong commitment to professionalism, collaboration, and organizational values. This commitment is supported by their conscientiousness and strong work ethic, which demonstrate their ability to manage responsibilities effectively despite challenges. The positive organizational climate and culture, further contribute to mitigating counterproductive behaviors among solo parents, fostering a conducive work environment that promotes mutual respect and trust.

3. That the importance of understanding legal provisions such as the Solo Parents' Welfare Act and their impact on workplace dynamics is important. As awareness increases, so does work performance.

4. That Solo Parent Awareness Action Plan is proposed to enhance a reasonable level of awareness of the RA8972 while simultaneously increasing solo parent employee work performance and confidence levels.

Recommendations

1. To address the low awareness regarding Benefits & Privileges and Factors affecting the implementation of RA 8972, XYZ Corporation may prioritize educational initiatives and awareness campaigns aimed at informing solo parent employees about their rights and entitlements. It is crucial to take proactive steps to bridge this awareness gap, such as conducting training sessions, distributing informational materials, and demonstrating a commitment to supporting solo parent employees and promoting a workplace environment that values equity, respect, and employee welfare. Additionally, there is a need to deepen comprehension of the act's implementation complexities. Addressing this knowledge gap empowers solo parent employees to navigate challenges in accessing their rights under the act effectively.

2. There is a need to address potential barriers hindering solo parent employees from fully engaging in contextual performance activities by implementing a targeted training program at XYZ Corporation. This program may focus on enhancing contextual performance skills, providing strategies and tools to improve adaptability to role demands, navigating workplace dynamics effectively, and integrating seamlessly into team environments. By investing in the development of these skills, XYZ Corporation can empower solo parent employees to enhance their overall work performance, contributing positively to the organization's success.

3. The organization may implement comprehensive actions, including conducting awareness workshops, advocating for community engagement, enhancing support services, promoting cultural sensitivity, and providing training for Barangay Development Council members. These initiatives aim to educate solo parent employees about their rights under RA 8972, prioritize solo parent issues in the community agenda, advocate for comprehensive support services, foster a supportive environment, and increase the capacity of local authorities to effectively support solo parents. By implementing these measures, XYZ Corporation can create a more inclusive and supportive work environment for solo parent employees, ultimately enhancing their well-being and work performance.

4. XYZ Corporation may consider the specified action plan or program to further develop and enhance the awareness of solo parents and their work performance, this is to aid them in cultivating a nurturing and inclusive atmosphere for solo parent employees, ultimately elevating their performance and holistic welfare. By incorporating this action plan, XYZ Corporation can play a role in empowering and satisfying its solo parent workforce while adhering to the stipulations of RA 8972.

5. There is a clear scarcity of literature on the subject, more research on the awareness of solo parent employees to RA 8972, as well as work performance should be

done. It is also recommended that a qualitative strategy rather than a quantitative approach be employed in future research with the purpose of better understanding the solo parents' experiences. XYZ Corporation may have a great opportunity to do all necessary analyses about the awareness of solo parents to RA 8972 and their work performance as a result of this initiative.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In the study conducted with solo parent participants in XYZ Corporation, strict adherence to ethical principles was maintained throughout the research process. Before the study commenced, comprehensive details regarding the research purpose, procedures, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality measures, and participants' rights were meticulously communicated to all solo parent participants. Informed consent forms were diligently obtained from each participant to ensure their voluntary participation and comprehensive understanding of their role in the study. Special measures were implemented to safeguard the confidentiality and anonymity of participants' responses, with meticulous removal or anonymization of personal identifiers from the collected data. Participants were unequivocally assured that their responses would be strictly utilized for research purposes and would remain confidential within the confines of the research team. Throughout the research journey, utmost respect and dignity were accorded to solo parent participants using the Data Privacy Act of 2012, with their autonomy and prerogative to withdraw from the study at any juncture being fully respected and honored.

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